

Chaos & Governance, Responses To The Uncertainty In The Three-Body Problem And Separation Of The Three Powers

Haochen Zhang

The High School Affiliated to Renmin University of China, Beijing, China

ABSTRACT

The article compares the three-body problem from the science fiction series "The Three-Body Problem" with the principle of separation of the three powers in modern political science by exploring the role and impact of "Three" in different contexts of uncertainty. The objective is to help the public better understand the fundamental principles of the social and political system, avoid political apathy, and promote the development and exploration of diversified democratic and political governance models worldwide. In celestial mechanics, the three-body problem refers to the unpredictability of three celestial bodies under mutual gravitational influence, and in the novel series, civilizations undergo rise and fall due to the instability of the star systems. In contrast, the separation of the three powers in modern political systems balances legislative, executive, and judicial branches to prevent concentration and abuse of power, ensuring legitimacy, stability, and efficiency. The article compares the instability caused by the three-body problem with the relative stability contributed by separation of powers through analyzing human responses to uncertainty: seeking certainty for survival and development or exploring possibilities through controlled uncertainty. Additionally, it discusses the role of uncertainty management in societal governance using examples of the French Revolution and the American separation of powers, highlighting the importance of public engagement and influence in avoiding chaos and promoting societal progress.

Keywords: *Three-Body Problem; French Revolution; American Revolution; Survival and Development; Chaos and Governance.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

France and the United States are representative countries of modern society for separation of powers. Regarding the comparative analysis of the sister revolutions of France and America, academia draws sharply different conclusions.

Qian (2007) noted that "Compared with the French Revolution, the American Revolution exhibited a smooth and uneventful character, with the republican system it established being orderly and enduring. Tracing back to their origins, the reason why these sister revolutions, occurring in the same era and pursuing similar ideals, exhibit such stark differences lies in the fact that the revolutions took place in societies with different traditions. The stability of the American Revolution stems from a tradition of autonomy spanning half a century and the national character it produced"

On the other hand, Gao (2024) claimed that "The concept of 'civilization' proposed by the Enlightenment in France and the issue of the 'old regime' raised during the era of the French Revolution reflect that the French Revolution grasped the essence of 'democracy', thus evolving into a genuine 'democratic revolution'. The American Revolution lacked a French-style view of civilization and therefore could not envision the future, emphasizing only the necessity of reclaiming the colonial autonomy stripped away by the mother country (by then abstracted as 'freedom rights'), without realizing the importance of curbing human greed to ensure social harmony, thus lacking genuine democracy in the true sense.

Recently, upon re-reading Mr. Cixin Liu's "The Three-Body Problem" series of science fiction novels, a sudden idea lingered in my mind: Is there some subtle logical and dialectical connection between the three-body problem and the separation of the three powers? Could we reflect on the fundamental success or failure factors of modern social systems or revolutions through the different responses of the Trisolarans (people living on the three-body planet) and human societies to the concept of "Three"?

2. The Three-Body Problem and the Fate of the Trisolarans

In physics, the three-body problem is a fundamental mechanical model in celestial mechanics. It refers to the problem of the motion laws of three celestial bodies, treated as point masses with arbitrary masses, initial positions, and initial velocities, under the influence of universal gravitation. It is now known that the three-body problem cannot be precisely solved; that is, it is impossible to predict all mathematical scenarios of the three-body problem, with only a few specific cases having been studied. The study of the three-body problem is considered one of the most challenging issues in dynamical systems due to its unpredictability and extremely complex chaotic nature.

"The Three-Body Problem" series of science fiction novels tell the story of human scientists on Earth and their encounters with the "Three-Body Civilization". The Three-Body Civilization exists in an unpredictable stellar system, which has brought chaos to the highly developed civilizations of the three-body star system. These civilizations alternate between the "Stable Era" and the "Chaotic Era".

Within the civilization of the Trisolarans, history is divided into the "Stable Era" and the "Chaotic Era". The "Stable Era" refers to their planets orbiting around a single star, like our earth world with day and night, experiencing seasons, and allowing civilizations to thrive. All other times are the "Chaotic Era", characterized by extreme conditions such as unbearable heat (from two suns) or perpetual cold (with no sun). The Trisolarans survive the "Chaotic Era" by dehydrating themselves and awaiting the return of the "Stable Era", where they revive themselves with water. However, the appearance of three suns in the sky would lead to the extinction of their civilization, as the surface temperature of their planet would burn up the dehydrated Trisolarans. Unfortunately, the Three-Body Civilization has experienced extinction over a thousand times.

To ensure their survival, the Trisolarans begin to explore the universe and discover Earth's civilization, which perpetually exists in the "Stable Era". To escape the fate of repeated extinctions, they decide to colonize Earth. On the way to immigrate to this new home, the Trisolarans encounter fierce and organized resistance from humans on Earth, as well as various threats from outer space. Nevertheless, they remain steadfast in the belief in conquering a new homeland in space to continue their civilization with their technology advantages.

3. The Historical Development Background of Separation of the Three Powers

The basic idea of the separation of (three) powers is to divide the government powers into three independent branches: executive power, legislative power, and judicial power. Mutual checks and balances are designed to prevent abuse of powers, safeguard civil liberties, and improve the operation efficiency of government.

The origin of the separation of powers could be traced back to Greece and Rome times. Ancient political philosophers proposed the division of the state's functions into administration, deliberation, and trial. In medieval Europe, monarchs, churches, and nobles could also be seen as the precursor of the separation of powers.

During the Enlightenment in the 17th and 18th centuries, the theory of separation of powers got radical development with the outbreak of the bourgeois revolution and social environment changes. John Locke, a British Enlightenment philosopher, was the first to present the theory of decentralization. The French Enlightenment philosopher Montesquieu further refined it with his book "The Spirit of Laws", elaborating how the powers of the executive, legislative, and judicial branches should be separated to prevent despotism.

The United States was the first modern society adopting "separation of powers" as clearly stated in its Constitution. The Congress (House and Senate) owns legislation, the President undertakes administration, and the Supreme Court is responsible for judiciary. Such design could help to prevent excessive concentration of government power, reduce the risk of authoritarianism and dictatorship, and protect the rights and freedoms of its citizens.

As a matter of fact, separation of powers has been widely applied in social governance worldwide. For example, although the UK does not have a formal written constitution, the principle of separation of powers is reflected in its political practice, including the parliament, the prime minister and cabinet, and its independent legal authority. France, as one of the origin countries, also explicitly implements the separation of the executive, legislative, and judicial branches. Germany also follows the principle of separation of powers, with the government, parliament, and courts controlling the executive, legislative, and judicial branches respectively.

4. Analysis of the Chaos and Governance for Uncertainty

Why does the "three-body problem" mean instability while "separation of the three powers" introduces stability? In fact, "separation of powers", could also lead to significant uncertainty in some circumstances. The three powers sometimes cooperate and sometimes oppose each other, so it's hard to predict whether and when they could reach a consensus. We often read about governments and parliaments at odds over certain issues, debating for months or even years. Essentially, the involvement of "Three" inevitably brings about substantial uncertainty, even chaos.

4.1 Survival and Development: Pursuing Certainty or Uncertainty

Since the beginning of human history, from the Stone Age to the Agricultural Age, from feudalism to modern society, both individual families and society as a whole preferred to pursue certainty. However, certainty is not always superior to uncertainty. Exploring multiple possibilities and probing uncertainty can help humans navigate complex environments and maintain a balanced approach at the societal level.

K. Zhang and Q. Zhang (2011) pointed out that "Since the beginning of human society, there has been a pursuit of certainty. However, at different historical stages, people have different understandings of the root causes of uncertainty and different ways of pursuing certainty" and "In the pursuit of certainty, the scheme proposed by social contract theory is a principle and path of social construction for modern times, but it has never eliminated uncertainty" (p. 138).

When faced with threats to survival, ensuring survival takes precedence over development. In such cases, humans are forced to choose certainty. The Trisolarans face the problem of survival and the destruction of their civilization. They have to explore the universe, seeking planets more suitable for habitation to ensure the continuation of life and civilization. On the other hand, separation of powers, since the advent of capitalist society, signifies that society no longer

prioritizes basic survival conditions as its primary objective, but rather establishes a mechanism to seek social development and advancement.

Therefore, we could find that both the three-body problem and the separation of powers bring uncertainty to the Trisolarans and humans. The Trisolarans chose to escape to avoid the catastrophic uncertainty brought by the three-body problem. Similarly, separation of powers also brings uncertainty to humans, who, with survival assured, hope to leverage this uncertainty to drive social progress.

4.2 Influence and Engagement: Avoiding Chaos for Uncertainty, Seeking Governance

Humans inherently prefer certainty, so how should we seek certainty in an uncertain environment?

The Trisolarans' approach to dealing with the "Chaotic Era" is dehydration, waiting for the dawn of the 'Stable Era', and then rehydrating to revive themselves. They repeatedly invent various calendars to predict and estimate the cycles of stable and chaotic eras. After countless attempts, they ultimately have no choice but to flee the chaos brought by the three-body problem, seeking survival certainty by colonizing our Earth. The root cause here is that the Trisolarans cannot exert any influence over the three-body system, so they have to endure this uncertainty passively.

In contrast, separation of powers is entirely different. Although each branch of power appears to be dominant in its own sphere, they are fundamentally influenced by the general citizens. Moreover, each branch is designed with systems for public participation, including elections of power representatives, public participation in decision-making processes, media oversight, and various forms of checks and balances. The separation of powers system is not unreachable, uncontrollable, or non influenceable for the broad masses, unlike the superior stars for the Trisolarans.

From the analysis above, while both the three-body problem and separation of powers bring uncertainty, separation of powers largely ensures public participation and influence through

institutional design, effectively managing and controlling uncertainty. The ingenious design facilitates the harnessing and value creation of uncertainty.

Chen (2023) explained that "The world has entered the 'Uka era' and high-risk society, and the theory and practice of public governance are undergoing profound changes. Concepts and themes such as uncertainty, vulnerability, resilience, robustness, and adaptability are increasingly important and significant in public governance" (p. 68).

So, for each individual, regardless of the political system adopted by the country, actively participating in democratic political life is crucial to maximizing societal governance and human right protection.

4.3 Case Studies of Success and Failure in History

1) French Revolution: Pursuit of Uncertainty and Lack of Control

In history, the French Revolution can be deemed as a clear pursuit of uncertainty, where radical revolutionaries overthrew monarchy to try to establish a republic controlled by the people. However due to lack of influence on the regime they fought for, the situation quickly spiraled out of control.

Qiqun Zhang (2016) wrote that "Shortly, the revolutionary faction split into the Girondins and Jacobins, with the Jacobins accusing the Girondins of treason. Following mock trials, many Girondins were guillotined. Robespierre and his followers thereafter enforced harsh measures, immediately arresting anyone suspected of plotting against the Republic. Revolutionary tribunals executed numerous dissidents, with around 40,000 people across the nation losing their lives by the guillotine, and countless others arrested on false accusations. Priests who refused to swear were subjected to unprecedented persecution. Terror gripped the entirety of France, leaving no one feeling safe. By the end of 1793, the revolutionary government had largely stabilized France through a reign of fear. Paradoxically, in July 1794, Robespierre was overthrown and executed by the guillotine."

Throughout the French Revolution, there was a lack of institutional design for popular participation, making political decisions largely irrelevant to the people, who mostly existed in a state of passive acceptance and compliance. From the monarchy of Louis XVI, through the successive waves of revolutionary factions including the Girondins, Jacobins, and Thermidors, culminating in Napoleon's Brumaire Coup, it is akin to the incessant emergence of stars in the three-body problem introducing several "Stable Eras", interspersed with unexpected "Chaotic Eras".

For French people at that time the survival needs took precedence. They were eager for stability and security. In such a sense the French ultimately chose stability, symbolized by the certainty of Emperor Napoleon.

The failure of the French Revolution stemmed not only from radical political change but also from a lack of participation and influence from the public. While the old governance system was overturned, they failed to establish a mechanism to empower the people which led to a vacuum of power and subsequent loss of control. This transformation inevitably descended into chaos and failure since lacking solid public foundation and deep societal involvement. The French Revolution exemplifies the consequences of pursuing uncertainty without substantive public involvement.

2) Separation of Powers in the United States: Balancing and Advancing in Chaos

With centuries of development, the separation of powers in the U.S. political system demonstrates how people can drive social progress via deep engagement and effective checks and balances in chaos. The American people influence national decision-making processes directly or indirectly by elections, public opinion, protests and legal actions. Despite it often accompanied with fierce debates and conflicts, this kind of active political engagement propels continuous advancement and reform for their society.

As examples, the civil rights movements, the women's rights movements, and the recent environmental protection movements have all prompted legislative and policy adjustments through extensive public participation and advocacy in U.S. history. With the complex

institutional system design, the American people could navigate their direction forward through chaos and arguments, lifting the nation toward higher levels of civilization and development.

This institutional design has been continuing to contribute value in the development of American history as Qian (2007) explained, "In the United States, due to the habit of diversity and contradictions in autonomous politics, people consider the occurrence of conflicts and competition among interest groups as normal phenomena, and accept the idea that 'government is conflicts'" and "Such people know the meaning of government, understand the mysteries of politics, and accept that politics is an art of patching up" (p. 20-23).

Different interest groups, political parties, and even ordinary citizens are enabled to express their opinions and desires within this framework, despite it may lead to a more complicated policymaking process. Every decision undergoes thorough debate and examination which helps to safeguard long-term stability and development. This complexity, in another sense, does reflect the diversity and democratization of the society.

These two cases showed the complex relationship between governance and chaos in the situation of uncertainty. Uncertainty could be a fundamental impetus for social development. In practice, it's crucial to ensure that the public has sufficient influence and control to avoid chaos. When the uncertainty is effectively managed, it becomes a powerful factor driving social advancement, as the U.S. separation of powers system does. Otherwise, the uncertainty may lead to inevitable disasters, like the reign of terror during the French Revolution.

5. CONCLUSION: The Vibrant Vitality after Three Begets all Things

"Tao begets one, one begets two, two begets three, and three begets all things", stated in Chapter 42 of Lao-tzu's "Tao Te Ching". This ancient philosophical viewpoint brings us profound reflections on the origin of the universe and life. The "Three" here not only symbolizes the proliferation and vitality of all things, but also potentially harbors chaos and disorder.

This article conducts comparative research from a unique perspective that blends science fiction with reality, exploring the role and impact of the uncertainty associated with the concept of "Three" in various scenarios. It could help the public better understand the basic principles of the social and political system, prevent political apathy, and advance the development and exploration of global political governance to seek more diversified democratic models of "governance amidst chaos".

The separation of powers is not the sole mechanism for political governance nowadays. Discussions on the three-body problem and the separation of powers can still remind us to avoid the pitfalls of the three-body dilemma in modern society. Key to this is active participation of each individual and their influence over power. As the fundamental unit of society, people should deeply engage in political systems, exerting their own influence and perspective.

In practice, although the United States' system of checks and balances has historically demonstrated its effectiveness and flexibility, it currently faces severe challenges and issues, particularly due to lower levels of citizen participation. Political apathy and low voter turnout have made decision-making and policy formulation less comprehensive and equitable.

Actually, for most of the political systems worldwide, actively encouraging greater participation of the people to promote and explore comprehensive democracy is becoming the top priority to ensure sustainable innovation and development.

Moreover, as a prospect for future research, exceptional science fiction not only offers entertainment but also stimulates reflections among readers on technology, society, and the future of humanity. It enables us to understand and act upon these reflections on a deeper level, both broadly and precisely, and even inspires innovative designs for foundational principles in political, economic, and cultural realms of human society. For instance, the "Dark Forest Law" from Cixin Liu's "Three-Body Problem" and the nuclear non-proliferation principle currently under challenge within the international community, the "Three Laws of Robotics" from Asimov's "I, Robot" and the AI ethics issues arising from the current boom of large-language models—all represent fields deserving enlightening and divertive study.

REFERENCES

- Chen, Z. (2023). Practical changes and model reconstruction of public governance in the "Uka era": Effectively addressing governance challenges in high-risk societies (in Chinese). *Southeast Academic Research*, 6, 68–77.
- Dunn, S., & Yang, X. (Translator). (2015). *Sister revolutions: French lightning, American light*. The Commercial Press.
- Fan, J. (2023). The world construction and cosmic ethics in *The Three-Body Problem*: Cixin Liu's cosmic sociology (in Chinese). *Exploration and Contention*, 10, 126–135, 179.
- Gao, Y. (2024). Another comparison of the American and French revolutions (in Chinese). *Studies in Modern World History*, 00, 159–176, 363–364.
- Liu, C. (2008). *The Three-Body Problem*. Chongqing Publishing House.
- Mansu, Q. (2007). The American Revolution: Half a century of preliminary preparation (in Chinese). *Social Sciences Forum (Academic Review Volume)*, 12, 18–24.
- Montesquieu, & Ou, Q. (Translator). (2016). *The spirit of the laws*. Yilin Press.
- Wang, T. (2023). *The Three-Body Problem* and social cooperation (in Chinese). *Journal of Intelligent Society Research*, 5, 38–58.
- Zhang, K., & Zhang, Q. (2011). The historical footprint of human pursuit of certainty (in Chinese). *Zhejiang Academic Journal*, 2, 138–145.
- Zhang, Q. (2016). Schiller's remark on the violence of the French Revolution (in Chinese). *China Reading Weekly*, 2016-09-07(13).